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INFLUENCE OF STORE DISPLAYSON IMPULSE BUYING OF APPARELS AMONG YOUTH IN BANGALORE

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ABSTRACT :

Purpose-The present research aims to study the influence of visual merchandising on the impulse buying tendency of young customers' in apparel outlets. The effects of various displays in the retail stores to attract the store traffic were studied.

Design/methodology/approach – Data were gathered from 677 shoppers using mall intercept method in top six malls across Bangalore city. The statistical tools used for data analysis are Cronbach's α reliability test, principal component analysis, and multiple linear regression analysis.

Findings-The results proved that the eye catching window displays, mannequin displays and promotional signage statistically significantly predicted impulse buying tendency.

Research limitations/implications- As the study area is limited to Bangalore city and only four techniques of visual merchandising have been studied, the findings may lack generalizability. Further studies are needed to cover a larger geographical area and to test the effect of other internal and external triggers for impulse buying.

Practical implications-The findings of the study suggest

that in order to get positive reactions from customers, apparel retailers should design attractive displays to enhance the attractiveness of the products.

Originality/value-This study fulfills an identified research gap to test the effect of various visual merchandising displays on customers' impulse buying tendency among youth in Bangalore.

KEYWORDS : Impulse buying, Visual merchandising, Retailing, Displays, Shopping.

INTRODUCTION

The retail industry is changing rapidly and becoming more complex due to various trends such as changing demographics, household downsizing, more educated consumers, and emergence of new channel formats. Thus, there is a need that the retail industry must rapidly change existing techniques, approaches and strategies to satisfy the needs of future consumers in order to be successful and profitable. Retailers need to give emphasis on all the elements of their retail setting which includes store design and atmospherics. Due to stiff competition in the marketplace and similar nature of the products, apparel retailers are using visual merchandising tools to increase the attractiveness of their products.

The evolution of visual merchandising has brought about a new way of shopping. It resulted in a shift from verbal engagement between retailers and customers to sensory experience. Visual merchandising is creating a huge impact on customers' buying behavior in the form of impulse purchases, and thereby increasing the sales (Mehta and Chugan, 2012; Bashar and Ahmed, 2012). In the present situation visual merchandising has become the lifeline of the apparel industry. This research has focused on the study of customers' apparel impulse buying behavior among youth, as they constitute a large portion of the market, which is constantly growing (Shim, 1996) and little academic research exists about this segment. Most of the times buying decisions are unplanned and thus retailers need to realize the importance of point-of-purchase marketing activities. Attractive displays and promotional signage capture the attention of consumers and induce them to make impulse purchases. Retailers rely on merchandise displays to

draw consumers into the store and make them to notice, touch, evaluate and at last end up with a purchase. Displays have the ability to increase the sales and thus understanding of how consumers view and respond to merchandise displays has both academic and practitioner significance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research studies have shown that unplanned purchases account for up to 60% of all purchases (Mattila and Wirtz, 2008; Inman and Winer, 1998) and impulse purchases can account for anywhere from 40% to 80% of purchases depending on the product category (Hausman, 2000). The fact that unplanned, and specifically, impulse buying, accounts for a sizable percentage of all purchases are supported by recent industry research. Research by Coca Cola has shown that impulse buying accounts for more than 50% of all grocery purchases (CNBC, 2009). Impulse buying has been recently defined "as a sudden, hedonically complex purchase behavior in which the rapidity of the impulse purchase precludes any thoughtful, deliberate consideration of alternative or future implications" (Sharma et al., 2010). Thus, it is a vital phenomenon for researchers in consumer behavior and retailing (Piron, 1991). Stern (1962) gave a classification of planned, unplanned and impulse purchase. Planned purchases involve information search, rational decision making and more time consuming, whereas unplanned purchases are the one made without any prior planning. Impulse buying is different from unplanned buying in terms of quick decision making. Piron (1991) describes impulsive purchasing with four criteria: impulsive purchasing is unplanned; the immediate nature of the behaviour; the consumer experiences emotional and/or cognitive reaction; behaviour arise emotional reaction. Bayley and Nancarrow (1998) defined impulse buying as a "sudden, compelling, hedonically complex buying behavior in which rapidity of an impulse decision process precludes thoughtful and deliberate consideration of alternative information and choices". Rook and Fisher (1995) define impulsive purchasing as the consumer's tendency to perform spontaneous, unconsidered and sudden purchases. Past studies have focused on the definitional elements of impulse buying, and distinguished it from non-impulse buying. Impulse buying has also been related to demographic characteristics such as consumers' age, gender (Kollat and Willet, 1967; Rook and Hoch, 1985). Researchers have made an attempt to develop and measure the impulse buying tendency (Rook and Fisher, 1995; Weun, Jones, and Beatty, 1997). Impulse buying is triggered by both internal and external stimuli in the retail environment. Rook (1987) states, that impulsive buying behavior is based on a sudden stimulus, followed by excitement and/or pleasure and/or an irresistible urge to buy. Beatty and Ferrell (1998) stated that consumer's positive emotions are motivators to buy on impulse and thus impulsive buyers are more emotional. The factors stimulating consumers in the store are aroma (Mattila and Wirtz, 2008), sound/music (Holbrook and Anand, 1990) or colors (Valdez and Mehrabian, 1994). Han et al., (1991) found that high degree of involvement in fashion stimulates to buy impulsively because of existing experience and sensual signals. Consumers are more likely to buy on impulse when they are motivated by hedonic needs such as pleasure, novelty, surprise, fun and emotional excitement.

Visual merchandising is the art of implementing attractive displays to increase the store traffic and sales volume. It is a significant promotional tool used in fashion marketing to educate, inform, entertain and persuade shoppers (Lea-Greenwood, 1998). Kerfoot et al. (2003) investigated the impact of VMD stimuli on brand recognition, browsing, purchase intentions, and liking for displays in women's apparel stores. In-store design consists of mannequin displays, floor merchandising, promotional signage, and shelf displays. The research found that hanging and mannequin displays supported shoppers visualize outfits and encouraged multiple purchases and browsing (Kerfoot et al, 2003). Windows are the first impression of the store and thus are a significant element of the retail mix. Window displays are used to convey messages about the store, the brands it carries (Sen et al., 2002), variety and availability. Thus, they help the prospective consumers to decide whether to enter into the store. Edwards and Shackley (1992) found that sales increased when stores used window displays compared to without window display, and larger window displays were more successful in attracting consumers' attention than smaller ones. Successful window displays were more aesthetically pleasing, had a theme, used warm colors, appropriate lighting and incorporated accessories associated with products. Visual merchandising is one of the most important but understudied areas in retailing research. Vinamra et al. (2012) have studied impact of visual merchandising on consumer behaviour towards women's Apparel and found that visual merchandising has a very strong impact on customer purchasing behavior and to some extent visual merchandising also leads to impulse

buying.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES:

This research addresses the gap in the extant literature by studying the impact of visual merchandising on the customers' impulse buying tendency among youth. Therefore, hypotheses were framed to examine the associations between customers' impulse buying tendency (dependent variable) and the four visual merchandising activities (independent variables).

H₁: Window displays influence customers' impulse buying tendency.

H₂: Mannequin displays influence customers' impulse buying tendency.

H₃: Floor merchandising influences customers' impulse buying tendency.

H₄: Promotional signage influence customers' impulse buying tendency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research started with the collection of secondary data from various sources and then personal interviews with practitioners and academicians to state the research problem. A structured questionnaire was developed to gather the primary data.

INSTRUMENT DESIGN:

The first part of the questionnaire measured age, gender, occupation, marital status, educational qualification and individual monthly income of the respondents. Section 1 through 5 contained 27 scale items drawn from the existing research (Rook and Fisher, 1995; Beatty and Ferrel, 1998; Youn and Faber, 2000; Rook and Hoch, 1985; Weun, Jones, and Beatty, 1997; Han, 1987), to measure respondents' attitude towards various visual merchandising activities (independent factors) and impulse buying tendency (dependent factor). The responses were measured using a five point Likert scale ranging from 1 = never to 5 = always and a score of above 3 on this scale was considered to support the scale item.

SAMPLE DESIGN:

The survey was administered using a mall intercept method to collect the data in top six malls ranked on the basis of number of visitors of Bangalore city over a period of one month. Thus the sampling methods are convenient and judgement sampling. More than 800 shoppers were contacted, but only 700 shoppers cooperated and out of 700 filled questionnaires, 677 questionnaires were applicable for analysis. Remaining 23 questionnaires were discarded as they were incomplete and illegible.

DATA ANALYSIS METHODS:

Descriptive statistics were carried out for demographics and the scale items (dependent and independent variables). Exploratory factor analyses with Varimax rotation were used for multi-item scales. Items with factor loadings of at least 0.50 were retained to ensure the presence of reliable items (Nunnally, 1978). Items which were cross-loaded on more than one factor were discarded from further analyses. To test the hypotheses multiple regression analysis was used.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION:

Descriptive statistics were carried out to check the data entry errors and to describe the demographics of the respondents as shown in table-1. The majority of the respondents were in the age range of 21-25 years (54.1%). 52.7% of the respondents were male and 47.3% were female, thus gender parity was considered without favoring one gender over the other. The majority of the respondents were single, college going students and thus were dependent on parents' or others' income.

RELIABILITY TEST:

The Cronbach's α reliability test of 7 items in the impulse buying scale indicated that discarding item 4 and 7 would improve the overall reliability from 0.538 to 0.665. An analysis of the table-2 brings out that, the items on

impulse buying scale have an acceptable level of internal consistency (given the thumb rule of $0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$. while the various items indicating the factors influencing impulse buying have good internal consistency (given the thumb rule of $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.9$ for this).

Table-1:Demographic profile of respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	16 – 20 years	165	24.4
	21 – 25 years	366	54.1
	26 – 30 years	126	18.6
	31 – 35 years	20	3.0
	Total	677	100.0
Gender	Male	357	52.7
	Female	320	47.3
	Total	677	100.0
Occupation	Employed	285	42.1
	Unemployed	45	6.6
	Professional	29	4.3
	Business/others	13	1.9
	Student	305	45.1
	Total	677	100.0
Marital Status	Single	591	87.3
	Married	86	12.7
	Total	677	100.0
Educational Qualification	Intermediate	226	33.4
	Graduation	231	34.1
	Post-Graduation	203	30.0
	Other	17	2.5
	Total	677	100
Income	Below Rs. 10,000	52	7.7
	Rs. 10,000-25,000	178	26.3
	Rs. 26,000-50,000	86	12.7
	Rs. 51,000 and above	37	5.5
	Dependent on parents' or others' income	324	47.9
	Total	677	100

Table-2: Reliability Test

Test#	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Impulse Buying	5	0.665
VM factors in fluencing impulse buying	20	0.814

EFA output:

Using principal component analysis and Varimax with Kaiser Normalization rotation method, factor analysis of the 20 items of the scale was done. The KMO was 0.838 indicating that the data were sufficient for factor analysis. The Bartlett’s test of sphericity $\chi^2 (190) = 2790.822, p < 0.000$ showed that there were patterned relationships between the items. Two items: “I tend to buy the clothing which is on window display” and “Before entering a store, I usually check out its window displays” were removed from the final analysis as they were not significant in the model. The final factor solution emerged and the rotated factor matrix has been obtained which resulted into five factors covering 55.24 percent of variability and the eigenvalues for all the factors were above 1.0. It can be noticed from table-3 that 5 items load into the first component in the component matrix. The first rotated factor F1 with eigenvalue of 2.26 explaining 12.55% of the total variance can be interpreted as “Influence of Mannequin Display”. The average score for this factor is 3.03. It can be observed that Factor 2 with eigenvalue of 2.22 accounting for 12.31% of the total variance is grouping of 4 items and can be called as “Influence of Promotional Signage”. The average score for this factor is 3.16. For, Factor 3 with eigenvalue of 1.99 accounting for 11.03%, it is evident that there are 3 items which can be termed as “Influence of Eye-catching Window Display”. The average score for this factor is 2.96. Factor 4 with eigenvalue of 1.77 accounting for 9.85% has, again 3 items and labeled as “Influence of Informative Window Display”. The average score for this factor is 3.36. Factor 5 with eigenvalue of 1.71 accounting for 9.51%, has 3 items and can be termed as “Influence of Floor Merchandising”. The average score for this factor is 3.01. It is inferred that the dependent variable is influenced by

all the above mentioned factors.

Validity and reliability of EFA output:

The EFA output was tested statistically for validity and reliability. The Cronbach’s a value was greater than 0.6 for all the factors indicating the reliability of the output (Table-3). Convergent validity was checked with the help of “Variance Extracted” (Table-3). Variance Extracted for all five factors is higher than 0.4. The final factor output shows the absence of cross loadings indicating the discriminant validity of the output.

Multiple Regression Analysis:

A multiple linear regression was run on the data to predict impulse buying tendency from four visual merchandising tools. The results of multiple regression analysis are shown in table-4. It is revealed that, the eye catching window displays, mannequin displays and promotional signage statistically significantly predicted impulse buying tendency. The remaining two independent variables (informative window displays and floor merchandising) did not add significantly in predicting the dependent variable (p > 0.05).

Table-3:Results of EFA

Items	Mean	SD	Factor loading	Reliability	Variance extracted
Mannequin displays			0.783	0.685	44.57
When I look at mannequin displays, I get an idea of what to buy	3.03			0.554	
When I see clothing with a new style /design on display, I tend to buy	2.96	1.235		0.655	
When I like the clothing displayed on mannequin, I tend to buy	3.16	1.176		0.644	
I rely on displays for deciding to buy the clothing	3.00	1.154		0.629	
Mannequin displays are useful for visualizing how clothes look on me	2.91	1.206		0.675	
Promotional signage			0.914	0.721	54.82
I tend to buy, when I see a good offer on promotional signage	3.16	1.303		0.773	
Sale/Clearance sign temptsme to look at the clothing	3.08	1.162		0.717	
When I see a special promotional sign, I look at that clothing	3.28	1.189		0.639	
I am likely to make an unplanned purchase if the clothing has a Sale/ Clearance sign	3.06	1.293		0.733	65.29
Eye-catching window displays			1.039	0.736	
By seeing an eye-catching window display, I tend to enter the store	2.96			0.747	
When I see an interesting window, display, I tend to enter the store	3.06	1.335		0.754	
I select the stores to shop basedon eye-catching window displays	2.93	1.222		0.608	56.70
Informative window displays			0.707	0.780	
Window displaysinform me about the latest fashion trends	3.78	0.844		0.755	
I look at window displays to know the brands store carries	3.13	0.941		0.690	
Window displays provide general impression of the store	3.16	1.037		0.607	56.07
Floor merchandising			0.942	0.781	
I tend to try the clothing that catches my eyewithout going through the whole section	3.01	1.377		0.605	
When I move along the aisle, I tend to look at the clothing close to me	2.80	1.159		0.719	
I tend to try the clothing that catches my eye,when I pass by	3.10	1.230			

Table-4: Result of regression analysis

	df	R ²	F	β	t	Sig.
Dependent Variable:						
Impulse Buying Tendency	671	0.269	49.426	0.000		
Eye Catching Window Display				0.220	5.7270	0.000
Informative Window Display				0.031	0.934	0.351
Mannequin Display				0.181	4.709	0.000
Floor Merchandising				0.060	1.579	0.115
Promotional Signage				0.221	5.688	0.000

ESTIMATED MODEL COEFFICIENTS:

The general form of the equation to predict impulse buying tendency from eye catching window display, mannequin display, floor merchandising and promotional signage is:

Predicted impulse buying tendency = 1.160 + (0.165 X eye catching window display) + (0.178 X mannequin display) + (0.186 X promotional signage)

HYPOTHESIS TESTING:

To test the hypotheses, eye catching window displays, informative window displays, mannequin displays, floor merchandising, and promotional signage were entered into the regression model as independent variables and customers' impulse buying tendency as the dependent variable. The overall model was significant ($R^2 = 0.269$, $F = 49.426$, $p < 0.001$) (Table IV). Eye catching window displays positively affected customers' impulse buying tendency ($\beta = 0.220$, $p < 0.001$). Therefore, the H1a was supported. However, Informative window displays did not predict the customers' impulse buying tendency ($\beta = 0.031$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the H1b was not supported. Furthermore, mannequin displays positively affected customers' impulse buying tendency ($\beta = 0.181$, $p < 0.001$). Thus, the H2 was supported. Floor merchandising did not predict the customers' impulse buying tendency ($\beta = 0.060$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the H3 was not supported. Finally, promotional signage positively affected customers' impulse buying tendency ($\beta = 0.221$, $p < 0.001$). Therefore, the H4 was supported.

CONCLUSION:

The main aim of this study is to know why customers buy on impulse and to examine the external factors, particularly visual merchandising displays that trigger customers' impulse buying tendency. The notion of how visual merchandising influences impulse buying in the store, has not been emphasized in the past researches. The research result evidenced that there were statistically significant associations between customers' impulse buying behavior and the three visual merchandising practices viz. eye catching window displays, mannequin displays and promotional signage. Thus, it can be concluded that these visual merchandising elements influence the apparel buying behavior of young customers in shopping malls. The findings of this study support the view that impulse buying occurs due to various visual presentations carried out by the apparel retailers. The results of this study can be valuable to apparel retailers for designing effective window and in-store displays to enhance the attractiveness of the merchandise and to create a favorable attitude towards the products among the shoppers.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS:

It is noticed that visual merchandising displays created in an apparel retail stores influence a consumer to approach that store and make a purchase. The results of this study provide practical implications for the whole apparel industry. They may also help the retailers to better understand the shoppers' behavior in the malls and to design effective merchandising strategies to attract the shoppers. The study makes it clear that visual merchandising activities increase the likelihood of impulse buying among mall shoppers. Observing the positive influence of visual merchandising on impulse buying, retailers need to work hard to create eye-catching window displays, mannequin displays and promotional signage to enhance buying decisions of mall shoppers.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH:

This research has a few limitations which need to be emphasized. The findings of this research are mall

specific and thus may not represent the general population of shoppers. The data were gathered in selected shopping malls in Bangalore and hence sample was geographically restricted. The sample chosen are in the age group of 16-35 years and thus respondents with all age groups and a different geographical area may produce varied results. Thus, future research could be conducted with other demographic and geographic profile which helps in thorough analysis of the concept and enhance the generalizability of the findings. The study has mainly focused on apparel category and thus generalizations cannot be made for other product categories. The effect of only four techniques of visual merchandising on impulse buying behavior has been studied. Studying the impact of other internal and external factors influencing impulse buying may help in understanding the nature of impulse buying.

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